

A STUDY ON WORK STRESS AMONG THE EMPLOYEES OF SMALL SCALE GARMENTS INDUSTRIES WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO TIRUPUR DISTRICT

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Abstract:

Stress can make an individual productive and constructive when it is identified and well managed. In times of great stress or adversity, it's always best to keep busy, to plow anger and energy into something positive. Positive attitude and meditation will be helpful for coping the stress. The main objective of the study is to find out the level of stress among the employees in small scale garment industries. A sample of 100 employees was purposively selected from Tirupur district. It is found that gender, and working experience of the employees has significant association with level of stress. The research concluded that stress free employees perform better, work harder, feel happier and have a long term commitment to the organization as compared to their counterparts.

Key Words: Stress, Productivity, Stress Management, Employees & Garments

Introduction:

The present world is fast changing and there are lots of pressures and demands at work. These pressures at work lead to physical disorders. Stress is inescapable part of modern life, work place is becoming a volatile stress factory for most employees and it is rightly called as the Age of anxiety. Stress has become significantly with the result of dynamic social factors and changing needs of life styles. Stress is man's adaptive reaction to an outward situation which would lead to physical mental and behavioral changes. Brain cells create ideas, Stress may kills brain cells. The truth is that not all stresses are destructive in nature. Appropriate amount of stress can actually trigger your passion for work, tap your latent abilities and even ignite inspirations. Stress is the emotional and physical strain caused by our response to pressure from the outside world. Common stress reactions include tension, irritability, inability to concentrate, and a variety of physical symptoms that include headache and a fast heartbeat. Stress is a condition or feeling experienced when a person perceives that demands exceed the personal and social resources that an individual is able to mobilize. $S > P > R$ i.e., stress occurs when the pressure is greater than the resources. Stress is our body's way of responding to any kind of demand. It can be caused by both good and bad experiences. When people feel stressed by something going on around them, their bodies react by releasing chemicals into the blood. These chemicals give people more energy and strength, which can be a good thing if their stress is caused by physical danger. But this can also be a bad thing, if their stress is in response to something emotional and there is no outlet for this extra energy and strength.

Review of Literature:

Shiv Mohan (2012), in his study entitled "Job satisfaction and Job Stress; A study of the Hotel Industry in Delhi" stated that job satisfaction and quality of work life go hand in hand when talked about real satisfaction since one is the outcome of other. The basic objective of the study was to determine the gender difference in term of satisfaction with quality of work life between male and female workers. Also attempt is made to measure the level of quality of work life among the employees is made. It focuses on measures like job monotony, un clarity in goals, employee attrition, and role stress need to be properly handled.

NoopurSurtiand RiddhiAmbavale (2013), in their study entitled "A Study on Stress Level of Sales Employees in Garment Retail Stores of Ahmedabad City" revealed that there are various factors that affect job stress of the employees. Some of the major factors are health, work environment, job, emotional stability, personal relation, work load and appreciation and feedback. Out of these factors tests show that respondents have high stress based on factors health, emotional stability, personal relation, and appreciation and feedback. While low stress based on work environment, work load and job. It is also concluded that stress is high among the respondents, irrespective of age group they belong to or their gender.

Adetayojoshuaolusegun, Ajani john oluwasayo andolabisiolawoyim (2014), in their study entitled "an overview of the effects of job stress on employee's performance in Nigeria tertiary hospitals" stated that study is to appraise the cause of stress, the effect on employee performance, how workers identify those stress factors and react to the factors. The data of study was collected through the use of primary and secondary Sources by

administering questionnaires, personal interviews and information were extracted from relevant journals and statistical bulletins. The descriptive method was used to analyze the data with aid of frequency and percentage for the research objectives. The study concluded that job stress has significant effect on employees' performance.

R. Gomathi and R. Deepika (2013), in their study entitled "A Study on Stress Management among Employees at Sakthi Finance Limited, Coimbatore" conducted to find out the factor causing stress among employees and to know how they cope up with stress. The Research design used was a descriptive research. The primary data has been collected through a questionnaire method. The sample design used in the study was Convenience Sampling Technique with a sample size of 60. The collected data has been analysed through various tools like Percentage Analysis, Chi- Square Test& ANOVAs, and Factor Analysis.

Karan Singh Negi (2014), in their study entitled "Study of Work Stress in Employees of Business Organizations of Matsasya Industrial Area, Alwar District, Rajasthan" observed the work stress in lower and middle level employees of business organizations of Matsasya Industrial Area of Alwar district in Rajasthan. The study was conducted on basis of interviews and questionnaires based on stratified random sampling in some of the units of this industrial hub located near the NCR region. The study concluded that the various causes of work stress have been identified and tackling these would be useful for the management in enhancing work performance of their respective business organization.

Statement of the Problem:

Tirupur is an important trade Centre in India. It is famous for production of knit garment wears and it consist of a sequence of knitwear processing units such as knitting, dyeing, printing, embroidery, compacting, calendaring, cutting, stitching, ironing, packing, inspection and shipment. All these units are labor intensive and employees at all levels play a crucial role in processing garments to meet deadlines and buyer specifications. Long working hours, arduous work, amateur work climate, and low wages does not mar men and women from serving the industry for want of their livelihood. Under such circumstances, stress is a serious problem in the employees' life.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the demographic profile of the employees in small scale garment industries.
- ✓ To identify the level of work stress among the employees.

Research Methodology:

Tirupur District is the study area selected for this research. Primary data is collected through well-structured questionnaire. A sample of 100 respondents who were working in small scale garments in Tirupur District has been selected by using purposive sampling method. The collected information were reviewed and consolidated into a master table. For the purpose of analysis the data were further processed by using statistical tools. The statistical tools are

- ✓ Simple Percentage
- ✓ Chi-Square Test

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study is restricted to the selected employees of Tirupur District who were working in small scale garments industries and hence the result of the study cannot be generalized.
- ✓ The statistical methods used to analyze the data have their own limitation.
- ✓ All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Analysis and Interpretation:

1.1 Demographic Profile of the Employees:

Table no.1 describes the demographic profile of the employees for the study. Out of 100 respondents who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (63%) of the respondent are male, (57%) whose age group is under 26 to 50 years, most (68%) of the respondents studied up to School Level, the monthly income of (59%) respondents is between Rs.5,001 to Rs.10,000, (52%) of the respondents have 2 to 8 years working experience and (64%) of the respondents belong to nuclear family.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Employees

Factors	Number of Respondents N=100	Percentage
Gender		
Male	63	63
Female	27	27
Age (Years)		
Up to 25	14	14
26 to 50	57	57
Above 50	29	29
Educational Qualification		
Up to School Level	68	68
Graduate	21	21

Post Graduate	9	9
Monthly Income		
Up to Rs. 5,000	24	24
Rs.5,001 to Rs.10,000	59	59
Above Rs.10,000	17	17
Working Experience (Years)		
Up to 2 Years	33	33
2 to 8 Years	52	52
Above 8 Years	15	15
Type of Family		
Nuclear Family	64	64
Joint Family	36	36

Table 2: Relationship between the Employees Demographic Profile and level of work stress

Variables	Level of Work Stress			Total	χ^2 Value	Table Value	Remarks
	Low	Moderate	High				
Gender							
Male	13	22	38	63	7.634	5.991	S
Female	8	13	6	27			
Age (Years)							
Up to 25	4	5	5	14	2.499	9.488	NS
26 to 50	17	26	14	57			
Above 50	12	5	12	29			
Educational Qualification							
Up to School Level	09	37	22	68	6.178	9.488	NS
Graduate	10	13	8	21			
Post graduate	3	3	3	9			
Monthly Income (Rs)							
Up to Rs. 5,000	11	7	6	24	1.823	9.488	NS
Rs.5,001 to Rs.10,000	9	19	6	34			
Above Rs.10,000	14	18	10	42			
Working Experience (Years)							
Up to 2 Years	10	8	6	24	12.543	9.488	S
2 to 8 Years	20	21	18	59			
Above 8 Years	6	6	5	17			
Type of Family							
Joint Family	7	20	9	36	3.598	5.991	NS
Nuclear Family	18	34	12	64			

*significant at 5% percent level

1.2. Relationship Between the Employees Demographic Profile and Level of Work Stress:

Table no.2 depicts the relationship between selected demographic variables of the employees and Level of WorkStress. It is clear that , the calculated Chi-square value is less than the table value at five percent level, there does not exists any significant association between age, educational qualification ,monthly income, type of family and level of work stressamong employees in small scale garments. Thus the null hypothesis is accepted. It is clear that, the calculated Chi-square value is greater than the table value at five percent level, there exists a significant association between age, working experience of the employees, and level of work stress among employees in small scale garments. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion:

Stress in the work place has become the black plague of the present century. Much of the stress at work is caused not only by work overload and time pressure but also by lack of rewards and praise, and more importantly, by not providing individuals with the autonomy to do their work as they would like. Since the small scale garments industry is finance oriented, the management should arrange some stress managing programmes for their employee periodically. Small Scale Garment industries must begin to manage people at work differently, treating them with respect and valuing their contribution. If industries enhance the psychological well being and health of the employees, in the coming future the organization would make more revenue as well as employee retention. Because it is said that, "A Healthy Employee is a Productive Employee".

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